

A Feminist Study of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's *The Mistress of Spices*

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Abstract

Divakaruni's second novel The Mistress of Spices is a demonstration in magical realism of Hindu mythological and superstitions belief with the existing American social issues including, immigrant assimilation, spiritual emptiness among the rich Indians, teenage rebellion, forbidden inter-racial romances, abusive and broken marriage. This novel which is allegorical in nature, tries to dissolve the boundaries of prose and poetry. It is a supernatural story that deals with the magical powers of an ageless mystical woman Tilotamma. This article focuses on feminist study of Chitra Banerjee Divakaruni's The Mistress of Spices

Keywords: Identity, Racism, Struggle, Self-Perception, Restriction.

The story of *The Mistress of Spices* deals with two cultures of the Tilo, where Tilo is caught between her heritage and her new found world. The two edges that Tilo find herself caught up in the harsh reality of immigrant Indians in America and the mystical heritage of India. C. N. Eswari brings out the plight of women in a patriarchal society:

Women from the postcolonial world face double effacement of race and gender. Their lives are shaped not only by the western hegemonic discourse but also by the patriarchal discourse. Ironically, after independence from imperialism, the gender division in the once colonized nations became more prominent (214).

Divakaruni is able to cross the boundary of interdisciplinary and creates a new magical world. In India it is natural for the people to believe one's foremothers or grandmothers' folklore, stories and myth. Since, India is a store house of oral tradition from various section of the society. The novel does not deal only with the mystic nature of Tilo but its goes far deeper than the surface reading. It also questions one major issue of hybrid identity in a foreign country. The fantasy and the reality in the novel complement each other rather than separating them.

Tilo is allowed to work her spells and magic only within the confines of her grocery store and only on her Indian immigrant customers. Tilo the architect of immigrant dreams, life giver, restorer of health and hope. The spice shop, where the whole Indian

community converges is like a microcosm in itself. The novel is about the familiar immigrant tales of dreams, desires, pain and struggles which eventually end with hope. We see myriads of faces, there the bougainvillea girls, the rich men's wives and Mohan. Each face tells a story. Many of their immigrant dreams lie shattered in the dust, but there are also some success stories. The most vivid among them are the faces of four whose fates are inextricably linked with that of Tilo, the spice and spell marker: Lalita, Haroun, Geeta and Raven.

Tilo is incapable of self-perception and can only perceive her through the eyes of others when she lives in America. Though she fails in her effort to perceive herself, she succeeds in rendering her service to the mankind. She has an insight to understand others' problems and to help them in solving them. Tilo finds herself that she is composed of numerous identities. When she is trained on the island with other mistresses, she remains a silent spectator; she undergoes the purification silently by shampathi's fire and accepts her transformation into an old woman. Tilo carries over her thoughts to America. She is left with the memories of her past life in the island. She finds it difficult to suspend her thoughts about the island, first mother, the old woman and her training. During her training, first mother presents a knife to Tilo as a symbol of removing the memories and keeping her engaged in the present life to cut her moorings from the past, the future and to keep her always rocking at sea.

Tilo's diasporic journey begins when she is carried away by the pirates in a ship to the island. When she travels to the island, she doesn't feel the loss of home. She gets dislocated but does not long for her native place or her life with the family members. She finds many girls like her on the island. She meets the first mother, an elderly woman, training the mistresses to equip themselves to serve the mankind. First mother is represented as traditional and maternal figure, but trains the mistress to a progressive change. Thus, she is a juxtaposition of two elements of old and new trends differing geographical spheres, times and cultures. First mother tells them after their training that it is the time for getting new names for the mistresses. "Daughters it is them for me to give you your new names, for when you came to this island you left your old names behind, and have remained nameless since" (The Mistress of Spices 40).

Tilo loses her identity in her native land itself and receives new identity in the island. The first mother gives her the new identity as Tilo and transforms her into her own woman. Thus she is purified by the shampathi's fire before she is sent to Oakland, America. Divakaruni is again foreshadowing the process of Tilo's identity formation. Shampathi's fire is symbolized as phoenix, the legendary bird. As the bird gets life again from its ashes, the novelist has implied that Tilo recreates her after coming out of shampathi's fire. Tilo's journey to America is like her re-birth. Like the phoenix bird, she recreates herself to render service to the mankind. The ashes are found in her spices store as it reminds her about the past and are scattered as her remnants from where she raises. It is also symbolized as a substance reminding death and life linked together.

Divakaruni treats spices as characters in her novel as they listen and speak to Tilo. They react and restrict from using the magical powers. Tilo and the other women like her who become mistress are plopped down around on the world in little shops to sell spices one of the cruel tricks played on the mistress is that no matter their age, they exist trapped within the body of an aged woman. The spices do this in order to prevent their mistresses from being tempted by bodily bending the spices to help others in difficulties, however, when Tilo begins to feel the pleasures. Tilo uses spices to her own will, ignoring what they say she should prescribe, she discovers how quickly the spices can turn their magical powers against her. When she falls in love with raven all the magical powers she had from the spices and herbs begin to recede and hollow her bones. The spices song becomes a receding song. Though Tilo survives in America, she lives with the memories of the island and the first mother. It reminds her about her training and the instructions. After meeting raven, her

loves she hears first mother's voice often due to her guilty consciousness. Tilo interacts with her to justify the actions done on her interest. "The spice's silence is like a store in my heart, like ash on my tongue. Through it I can hear back to long ago, the old one laughing bitter as bile. I know what she would say where she here" (48).

The memories of her past do not simply haunt her but become the past of her. It is impossible for her in the present to live without the memories. The present itself is not the permanent one for her. This new sense of time is explained in the text, for Divakaruni jumps from one secular location within readers by every chapter. Divakaruni creates a somatic reaction within readers by oscillating between Tilo's childhood, her days spent on island, and the various stages of her life in America, causing us to experience the same sense of temporal dislocation. When Tilo comes to know about the brutality of racism, by reading in the newspaper, she splits seeds to heal the wound. Here Divakaruni once again mentions the existing racism in America. When Tilo thinks about the injured Mohan, she thinks: "O Mohan broken in body broken in mind by America, I come back from your story in pieces, find myself assembled at last on the on the chill floor of the shop" (30).

The story ends with Tilo's transformation into a middle aged woman and renamed her Maya, which means an illusion. Divakaruni indirectly points out that reality of the human condition is only an illusion. She also gives the hidden messages that no human being has real identity. Tilo chooses the name Maya that means many things. It is a name that consists of the multiplicity of her identities, various consciousnesses' that lie within her.

Divakaruni neither encourages complete assimilation with the host culture, nor stimulates alienation from the old culture. This novel teaches that the immigrant experience can be successful through the union of different cultural values. It also informs about the lives of Indian immigrants in America and about Indian culture, culinary culture in particular, and about the lives of Indian immigrants in America. Divakaruni perhaps also wants to show why Indian immigrants maintain certain aspects of their Indian culture even in America. In this manner she tries to evoke the readers' compassion and understanding for such immigrants.

In the feminist view, *The Mistress of Spices* deals with the sufferings and emotional battles inside the women in this society. The novel clearly states the problems faced by the women in foreign land and their inner conflicts in choosing their identity. For an immigrant it is not easy to adapt the cultural displacement and overcome it. Their inner dilemma makes them to strike between the Indian and American cultures. In this novel Chitra Banerjee, tells us about the hopes and dreams of Indian immigrants in the foreign land. Through her own experience she becomes well known about the differences in Indian culture and American culture as she herself moved to the United States from India. She portrays the adjustment through food and dress habits. As Fanon points out: "the native cannot talk to the western doctor accepting the (western man's) medicine is demonstrating confidence in western technique/ science, swallowing it in one gulp is literally getting even with it" (qtd in Nayar 173).

Self-perception is the foundation of identity within these texts, but the self that emerges from the various self-perceptions is not one characterized by double identities vying for unification. Rather, the South Asian diasporic women are comprised of multiple selves existing together, conflicting with each other but ultimately, to one degree or another, accepted in their contradictions by the women who possess them. The notion of a problematic double consciousness envisions a future synthesis of identity as a solution, where it is possible for a man to be both a Negro and an American, the women in the texts are examined and that reject such a synthesis.

Divakaruni develops a new narrative technique. The technique she adopts is a magical realism which aims to seize the paradox of the union of opposites. *The Mistress of Spices* stirs magical realism into the new conventions of culinary fiction and still-simmering caldron of Indian immigrant

life in America. The novel, also to a great extent, reveals Divakaruni's understanding of the human psyche, particularly female consciousness. Divakaruni, in her novel, *The Mistress of Spices* is actively engaged in the task of re-imagining the space for the diasporic community. In the voice of her heroine Tilottama, Divakaruni locates an authentic feminine voice which is at once a voice of power and gentleness that has made new in the diasporic location. It is by re-articulating south Asian American subjectivity re-inventing myths, relocating the power of the female voice and blending the real and the fantastic. Divakaruni's novel gives a cross-cultural experience of the south Asian Community in the United States.

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